
Chemical constituents and antimicrobial activity of essential oils from the leaves and stems of *Schefflera palmiformis* Grushv. & N. Skvorts

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Abstract Essential oils from the leaves and stems of *Schefflera palmiformis* (Grushv. & N. Skvorts.) were extracted by hydrodistillation and characterized by analytical gas chromatography and gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy. Thirty-nine (77.16 %) and thirty-three (82.21 %) components were identified from the leaves and stems, respectively. The most abundant compounds in the leaves were β -caryophyllene (15.29 %), caryophyllene oxide (6.17 %), germacrene D (6.06 %), spathulenol (5.97 %), and from the stem were germacrene D (36.51 %), δ -cadinene (7.69 %), α -copaene (6.65 %). The oil obtained from the stem showed weak antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords *Schefflera palmiformis*, essential oils, β -caryophyllene, germacrene D, antimicrobial activity

Introduction

The genus *Schefflera* is the largest genus of the Araliaceae family, consisting over 200 species distributed in tropical and sub-tropical regions and more than 50 of which can be found in Vietnam. Plants of this genus have been used in folk medicine for the treatment of pain, rheumatic arthritis, and sore throat [1]. Previous investigations on plants in the *Schefflera* genus led to the isolation of triterpenes, triterpenoid glycosides and saponins [2-5]. Furthermore, many pharmacological activities of the genus such as anti-inflammatory, anticancer and antiviral activities have been reported [6-9]. However, volatile oils from *Schefflera* plants have been little chemically analyzed. The oils of *S. stellata*, *S. heptaphylla* were found to contain β -caryophyllene, β -pinene as their major constituents [10-11]. *Schefflera palmiformis* (Grushv. & N. Skvorts.) is an endemic tree to Vietnam and threatened by habitat loss [12]. The chemical composition of this plant has not been studied. In the present paper, we report the chemical composition of essential oils from the stems and leaves of *S. palmiformis*. The antimicrobial activities of the volatile oils were evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Plant Materials

The leaves and stems of *Schefflera palmiformis* (Grushv. & N. Skvorts.) were collected in November 2017 in Thach Thanh district, Thanh Hoa province, Vietnam and authenticated by Dr. Dau Ba Thin, Department of Botany, Hong Duc University. A voucher specimen was preserved in the Department of Natural Sciences, Hong Duc University.

Extraction of essential oils

The essential oils were isolated from *Schefflera palmiformis* leaves and stems by hydrodistillation for 3 h in an all-glass Clevenger until no more essential oil was coming out and the oils were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

Analysis of the volatile oils

The chemical composition of the oils were determined by Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) on an Agilent Technologies HP 7980 Plus Gas chromatograph fitted with a fused silica capillary column HP-5MS column (30 m \times 0.25 mm, film thickness 0.25 μm , Agilent Technology) and interface with a mass spectrometer HP 5975 C spectrometry at the Department of Chemical Analysis, Institute of Natural Products Chemistry - Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology. The analytical conditions were: carrier gas H_2 (1 mL/min), injector temperature (PTV) 250°C, detector temperature 260°C, column temperature programmed from 60°C (2 min hold) to 220°C (10 min hold) at a rate of 4°C/min. The MS conditions were as follows: ionization voltage 70 eV; emission current 40 mA; acquisitions scan mass range of 35–350 amu at a sampling rate of 1.0 scan/s.

Identification of the Constituents

The chemical constituents of the volatile oils was identified by the comparison of retention indices (RI) with known essential oil constituents, mass spectra of MS library (NIST 08 and Wiley 9th Version), and with MS literature data [11].

Antimicrobial Activity

The antimicrobial activity of the oils were tested by disc agar diffusion method [13] on 3 strains of microorganisms Gram (+): *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Lactobacillus fermentum*; 3 microorganisms Gram (-): *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* fungi at the Applied Biochemistry Laboratory, Institute of Chemistry - Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology.

Results and Discussion

Chemical composition of essential oils

The essential oils obtained from the leaves and stem of *Schefflera palmiformis* were light yellow and pleasant smell with yield 0.13% and 0.20%, respectively.

The volatile oil of the leaves was analyzed by means of mass spectrometry (GC/MS), 39 compounds were identified accounting for 77.16% of total essential oil content from the leaves. Among them, 25 compounds belong to the sesquiterpene comprising 54.87 % of the total volatile constituents, 9 compounds belong to the oxygenated sesquiterpene constituting 19.62 % of the total volatile constituents, 4 compounds belong to the monoterpene with 2.25 % of total oil. As shown in Table 1, the sesquiterpene, β -caryophyllene is the major constituent (15.29%) in the leaves of *S. palmiformis*. Other dominated constituents are sesquiterpen compounds including germacrene D (6.06%), γ -muurolene (4.81%), α -humulene (4.55%), β -cis-elemene (3.53%), α -copaene (3.20%), α -muurolene (3.06%) and oxygenated sesquiterpenes like caryophyllene oxide (6.17%), and spathulenol (5.97%). Moreover, there are 30 components with content from 0.12-2.16% of the oil.

Thirty-three components representing for 82.21% of the total oil was identified from the stem essential oil. Similar to the leaf oil, the sesquiterpenes with 24 compounds were the most abundant in the stem oil (71.76%), followed by oxygenated sesquiterpenes (10.3 %, 8 components). Only a monoterpene, *o*-cymene (0.15%) was identified. The major constituents were sesquiterpenes germacrene D (36.51%), δ -cadinene (7.69%), α -copaene (6.65%), β -caryophyllene (4.66%), and α -cubebene (3.18%). In addition, 28 components with ratio from 0.14 -2.32 % of the total oil (Table 1).

Table 1: Chemical composition (%) of the leaf and stem oils of *Schefflera palmiformis*

No	Constituent	RI	Leaf (%)	Stem (%)
1	α -Pinene	939	0.13	-
2	Sabinene	978	0.49	-
3	Myrcene	992	1.44	-
4	<i>o</i> -Cymene	1030	0.19	0.15

5	δ -Elemene	1348	0.92	0.56
6	α - Cubebene	1360	0.40	3.18
7	α -Ylangene	1385	0.22	-
8	α -Copaene	1390	3.20	6.65
9	β -Bourbonene	1400	0.22	-
10	β - Cubebene	1402	-	1.00
11	β - <i>cis</i> -Elemene	1404	3.53	1.30
12	β -Copaene	1435	0.67	0.24
13	β -Caryophyllene	1438	15.29	4.66
14	Calarene	1446	2.03	0.53
15	Aromadendrene	1457	0.81	0.14
16	α -Humulene	1472	4.55	1.52
17	9- <i>epi</i> -(E)-Caryophyllene	1479	0.78	0.46
18	γ -Muurolene	1491	4.81	1.63
19	α -Amorphene	1495	0.30	-
20	Germacrene D	1499	6.06	36.51
21	β -Selinene	1505	0.74	0.21
22	γ -Amorphene	1510	0.28	0.23
23	<i>Trans</i> -Muurolo-4(14),5-diene	1513	-	0.33
24	Bicyclogermacrene	1515	-	1.73
25	Viridiflorene	1512	0.76	-
26	α -Muurolene	1514	3.06	-
27	γ -Cadinene	1531	1.18	0.55
28	δ -Cadinene	1537	2.16	7.69
29	<i>Cis</i> -Calamenene	1540	0.74	0.19
30	α -Cadinene	1554	0.36	-
31	α -Calacorene	1561	0.35	1.09
32	Germacrene B	1578	1.45	0.87
33	β -Calacorene	1582	-	0.22
34	3- <i>Z</i> -Hexenyl benzoate	1582	0.42	-
35	Spathulenol	1601	5.97	2.00
36	Caryophyllene oxide	1607	6.17	2.32
37	Salvial-4(14)- <i>en</i> -1-one	1616	-	0.71
38	Humulene Epoxide II	1633	1.94	-
39	1- <i>epi</i> -Cubenol	1649	1.13	1.02
40	T-Muurolol	1663	0.97	1.38
41	Eudesma-4(15),7-dien-1b-ol	1669	0.29	1.78
42	α -Cadinol	1676	1.35	-
43	<i>Cis</i> -Calamenen-10-ol	1680	1.06	0.21
44	<i>Trans</i> -Calamenen-10-ol	1689	0.74	-
45	Cadalene	1697	-	0.27
46	14-Hydroxy- δ -cadinene	1822	-	0.885
47	Sesquiterpenes		54.87 (25 components)	71.76 (24 components)
48	Oxygenated sesquiterpenes		19.62 (9 components)	10.3 (8 components)
49	Monoterpenes		2.25 (4 components)	0.15 (1 components)
50	% identified		77.16	82.21

The essential oils from the leaves and stem of *S. palmiformis* were tested for antimicrobial and antifungal activities on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans*. Only volatile oil from stems showed weak antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* at the concentration of 2mg/ml with diameter of the inhibition zone is 7 mm.

Conclusion

For the first time, the essential oils from leaves and stems of *Schefflera palmiformis* (Grushv. & N. Skvorts.) were investigated. The most abundant compounds in the leaves were β -caryophyllene (15.29%), caryophyllene oxide (6.17%), germacrene D (6.06%), spathulenol (5.97%) while germacrene D (36.51%), δ -cadinene (7.69%), α -copaene (6.65%) were major constituents in the stem. The stem oil showed weak antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Acknowledgements

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